

REFLECTANCE SPECTROSCOPY OF THE MOON: MAKING BETTER LUNAR ANALOGUES. E. A. Cloutis¹, D. Das¹, D. Applin¹, K. Peters¹, C. Tai Udovicic¹, A. Cunje¹, H. Vannier¹, T. Ledoux¹, and S. Lambert¹. ¹Centre for Terrestrial and Planetary Exploration, University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Avenue, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada R3B 2E9; e.cloutis@uwinnipeg.ca.

Introduction: Reflectance spectroscopy is a widely-used technique to explore the surface composition of the Moon. This technique can be applied to Earth-based observations [1], lunar orbiters [2], and landed missions [3]. It has long been known that the spectral reflectance properties of the Moon differ from those of analogue materials. This is largely due to the fact that “space weathering” on the Moon’s surface results in the production of nanophase/microphase iron (commonly termed npFe⁰). This material is concentrated on the surfaces of lunar grains [4]. The results of this is that reflected light is strongly affected by the finely dispersed surficial iron particles, as they can be strongly absorbing incident light.

While npFe is present in low abundances, <<1 wt.% [5], its concentration on grain surfaces strongly affects resultant reflectance spectra.

While there is a proliferation of lunar analogues, these materials are often designed to simulate some aspects of the lunar surface. We have examined the spectral reflectance properties of Apollo regolith samples as a guide to assessing the spectral qualities of lunar simulants.

Methods: To determine the spectral reflectance suitability of lunar analogues, we have measured the 350-2500 nm reflectance spectra of a suite of Apollo regolith samples (all <1 mm grain size) (**Fig. 1; Table 1**), as well as existing lunar regolith analogues, and continue to develop and characterize additional analogues as discussed below. We are also assessing whether powdered lunar meteorites can serve as lunar regolith analogues, as well as how surface-exposed lunar rocks differ from regolith samples.

Fig. 1. Reflectance spectra of Apollo regolith samples. Type and maturity are indicated in the legend.

Table 1. Apollo regolith samples in this study.

Sample	Description; % ilmenite	Is/Fe
10084	Mature mare basalt; 5.6%	78
12030	Immature mare basalt; 2.9%	14
15041	Mature mare basalt; 0.9%	94
61221	Immature highland; 0.6%	9.2
64801	Mature highland; 0.2%	82
71061	Immature mare; 9.2%	14

Results: The reflectance spectra of Apollo regolith samples are shown in **Fig. 1**. It can be seen that the highland samples are brighter than the mare samples and are red-sloped. Both show weak absorption features in the 950 and 2000 nm region, attributable to high-calcium pyroxene (HCP), which, while much less abundant than plagioclase feldspar, dominates any absorption features (plagioclase has only a weak absorption band in the 1300 nm region [6]. Increasing maturity leads to lower reflectance.

The mare regolith samples show overall reflectance than the highland samples, and are also all red-sloped. The mare spectra also show absorption features in the 950 and 2000 nm regions, again likely attributable to HCP. Increasing maturity again leads to darker spectra. Differences in mafic silicate band depths may be related to compositional differences.

Comparison of the highland regoliths to some highland analogues (**Fig. 2**) shows that these analogues can be as bright as immature highland regolith, but are not as red-sloped. The analogues can also exhibit mafic silicate absorption bands in the 950 and 2000 nm region (e.g., Shimizu HS highland simulant).

Fig. 2. Reflectance spectra of our two highland regolith samples and some terrestrial analogues.

A similar comparison of mare regolith to various analogues (**Fig. 3**), shows that they are either too bright and/or not as red-sloped.

Fig. 3. Reflectance spectra of Apollo mare regolith samples and some mare simulants.

Discussion: It is obviously an oversimplification that a single mare or highland analogues would be suitable for all lunar terrains. A high-fidelity lunar analogue should be compositionally similar to lunar regolith; this can be problematic because:

- Lunar mare mafic silicates are generally more Fe-rich than terrestrial equivalents, meaning that absorption band positions will vary between lunar and terrestrial minerals [7]
- Lunar regolith can contain substantial amounts of glass/agglutinates, which are rare in terrestrial equivalents; however, glasses can be spectrally similar in some wavelength regions [8,9]
- Lunar highland plagioclase is very An-rich, but this does not necessarily lead to substantially different spectra than more Ab-rich varieties [6].

Mismatches between lunar materials and terrestrial analogues can be partially compensated for. For instance the more Fe-rich nature of lunar mafic silicates, leads to known shifts in absorption band positions and depths for a given grain size [7].

The presence of npFe in lunar regolith is more problematic. It has an outsized effect on lunar regolith spectra, leading to darkening and reddening [10]. However, it appears that production of a spectrally-suitable space-weathered regolith is possible. Kohut et al. [11] have developed a method to produce mineral grains with surficial npFe, similar to lunar materials (however, lunar npFe is embedded in a silica-rich amorphous rind [4]). This procedure has been shown to work for producing spectrally lunar-like olivine and involves heating samples in air (which produces surficial iron oxide), then heating the samples in hydrogen to reduce the iron oxide to iron metal, and finally heating the sample in nitrogen gas with a few percent oxygen to passivate the npFe. We are investigating how similar procedures could be applied to other lunar minerals or mixtures.

Our ongoing investigation is also looking into how and whether crushed lunar meteorites are suitable spectral analogues for lunar regolith. This may be

possible because the available lunar meteorites in our study are all breccias, and may contain lithified regolith; this is being determined (Table 2).

Table 2. Lunar meteorites included in this study.

Meteorite	Description
Bechar 003	Feldspathic breccia
Gadamis 004	Anorthosite (FAN suite)
Laayoune 002	Feldspathic breccia
Lahmada 002	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 8277	Lunar; brecciated
NWA 10401	Anorthositic-troctolitic breccia
NWA 11182	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 11228	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 11303	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 11444	Melt breccia
NWA 11474	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 11788	Feldspathic breccia
NWA 12593	Fragmental
NWA 13788	Impact melt breccia
NWA 13964	Feldspathic breccia
NWA-misc	8 grams of saw-cut powder: various lunar meteorites

Additional insights into lunar regolith spectral properties are being derived from ongoing studies of a suite of surface-exposed Apollo rock samples (Table 3). We are comparing interior to exterior surfaces as well as to soils from the same landing sites.

Table 3. Apollo rock samples with space-exposed and interior surfaces included in this study.

Sample	Description
15555	Medium-grained olivine basalt
65015	Feldspathic impact melt breccia
71175	Equigranular ilmenite basalt

Summary: This combined analysis of various lunar samples will inform our development of high-fidelity lunar regolith analogues. Analogues are the only realistic option for producing >10s of gram samples for wide-ranging studies.

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Acknowledgements: This study was supported by the Canadian Space Agency (CW2421931; 9F057-240377) and the European Space Agency (4000xxxxx/25/NL/AS).